

Social and cultural closure in awarding the Nobel Prize in Physics

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The Nobel Prizes stand above all other awards in terms of both scientific prestige and public recognition. It is no surprise that they have attracted considerable scholarly interest since the first prizes were given out in 1901. For the sociologist Robert K. Merton (1968), the Nobels were indicative of what he termed “the Matthew Effect,” a general tendency in science towards prior success bringing with it a disproportionate share of later rewards. Merton’s initial conjecture has been confirmed in a great number of studies of scientific recognition, and similar processes of cumulative advantage have been observed in a variety of other social contexts. Yet the actual dynamics of recognition within elite scientific circles remain poorly understood. The Nobel Prize in particular retains an aura of mystery, its deliberations shrouded in secrecy until the moment the laureates are announced each year.

This research paper in progress aims to disentangle the social mechanisms behind the awarding of the Nobel Prize in Physics using newly available data sources and computational methods. It is part of a larger project entitled “The Matthew Effect revisited: the social and cultural dynamics of awarding the Nobel Prize,” which is funded by Riksbankens Jubileumsfond (MXM19-1229:1) and covers the prizes in science as well as in literature. Drawing a novel dataset of candidate nominations, publications, and social networks for the Nobel Prize in Physics from 1901 to 1966 – some of the most recent year available under the Nobel statutes – we examine the contributions of three different social processes to the selection of laureates by the Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences.

The first is cumulative advantage. The importance of the Matthew Effect in awarding the Nobel Prize seems self-evident. High citation counts and winning other prizes are both strongly associated with winning the Nobel Prize (Garfield & Welljams-Dorof 1992). But even where a Matthew Effect exists, its importance may decline as one approaches the top of a hierarchy. In their

initial studies of the Matthew Effect, Merton (1968) and Zuckerman (1977) called attention to “the phenomenon of the 41st chair:” wherever there is an honor with a limited number of recipients, one will also find worthy potential laureates who were passed over. Subsequent research has shown that cumulative advantage processes tend to become weaker and less predictable at the uppermost ends of the distribution (Garfield & Welljams-Dorof 1992, Gingras & Wallace, 2007). Gingras and Wallace (2007) find that it is nearly impossible to predict Nobel Prize winners using citations, at least after the 1960s.

The second is social closure. Social closure occurs if personal ties within the academic profession are mobilized to ensure that not all eminent scientists have a similar chance of winning the prize. Studies suggest that graduates of the most prestigious departments steer opportunities towards one another, ranging from prizes and honors to promising students and job openings (Bourdieu 1988, Zuckerman 1977). Prize scholars and even members of the Nobel committees have long decried the role of personal, national, and institutional loyalties in the selection process (Crawford 1992). Zuckerman (1977) found that over half of US Nobel laureates also studied with a laureate, leading to concerns about whether the laureates constitute a self-perpetuating elite (Crawford 1992). Yet Zuckerman’s striking finding is not unambiguous. Process of cumulative advantage can also concentrate promising researchers within a few leading institutes. And the Nobel awarding bodies, for their part, claim that they act to counter the biases of nominators.

The third is cultural closure, which occurs if prize judges and other gatekeepers impose preferences for research that is like their own. Scientific disciplines and specialty groups also compete for collective recognition (Bourdieu 2004). As Lamont (2009:8) has recently shown in the case of grant committees, academic evaluators “often

favor their own type of research while being firmly committed to rewarding the strongest proposal.” Far from being a departure from meritocratic norms, however, Accominotti (2018) suggests that a tendency towards cultural closure may be necessary for creating clear standards of evaluation and asserting a reliable hierarchy of worthiness. Studies of the Nobel Prize support the idea that the choice of winner depended on the predilections of committee members, at least in the earliest years of the prize (Friedman 2001). But little is known about the degree to which this effect persisted in later years, when committees were no longer struggling with a large backlog of nineteenth-century worthies.

Our analysis focuses on the final steps of the Nobel Prize selection process: the choice of a laureate from among the candidates put forward by the Nobel committee’s international network of nominators. In order to adjudicate between each competing social mechanism, we model the selection process using discrete choice methods. We measure cumulative advantage using counts of citations, previous prizes, and the nominations returned to the Nobel committee. We examine social closure in terms of both personal ties to previous Nobel laureates and the Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences as well as the degree of specifically national support the candidate enjoys, expressed by the percentage of nominations from co-nationals. Finally, to measure cultural closure we assigned candidates and judges to specialties using topic models of scientific publication titles.

The results show that cultural closure – the preference of judges for certain specialties within physics over others – plays an especially important role in prize decisions. Our findings are consistent with the existence of a strong and globally recognized hierarchy of research topics within physics, which persists even as judges attempted to award the prize to a wider array of specialties. In the production of scientific elites, the cumulation of advantage by individual scientists competes with the durable advantages enjoyed by scientific specialties, and to a lesser extent by specific research groups, institutions, and national communities.

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